

Towards an AI/ML-driven SMO Framework in O-RAN: Scenarios, Solutions, and Challenges

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Abstract—The emergence of the open radio access network (O-RAN) architecture offers a paradigm shift in cellular network management and service orchestration, leveraging data-driven, intent-based, autonomous, and intelligent solutions. Within O-RAN, the service management and orchestration (SMO) framework plays a pivotal role in managing network functions (NFs), resource allocation, service provisioning, and others. However, the increasing complexity and scale of O-RANs demand autonomous and intelligent models for optimizing SMO operations. To achieve this goal, it is essential to integrate intelligence and automation into the operations of SMO. In this manuscript, we propose three scenarios for integrating machine learning (ML) algorithms into SMO. We then focus on exploring one of the scenarios in which the non-real-time RAN intelligence controller (Non-RT RIC) plays a major role in data collection, as well as model training, deployment, and refinement, by proposing a centralized ML architecture. Finally, we identify potential challenges associated with implementing a centralized ML solution within SMO.

Index Terms—3GPP, Artificial Intelligence, Data Analytics, ETSI, Management & Orchestration, Machine Learning, O-RAN Architecture, O-RAN Alliance, Standards, SMO Framework

I. INTRODUCTORY REMARKS

THE rapid evolution of cellular networks towards open, virtualized, cloud-native, and slicing-aware architectures, exemplified by initiatives such as O-RAN, has introduced a new era marked by flexibility, scalability, programmability, automation, and intelligence in network management and service orchestration [1], [2]. The pivotal driver of this paradigmatic transformation is SMO within O-RAN. SMO encompasses management functions (MFs) introduced by the O-RAN Alliance, as well as those defined by other standards development organizations (SDOs) like the Third Generation Partnership Project (3GPP) and the European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI) [3]. These MFs, drawn from various SDOs, collectively provide management and orchestration (M&O) services for O-RAN components in a unified manner. SMO acts as a central nervous system, intelligently managing NFs, autonomously orchestrating resources, and efficiently optimizing network performance within O-RAN [4]. To that end, SMO seamlessly integrates artificial intelligence (AI)/ML algorithms into its operational architecture.

The integration of ML algorithms, trained through big data analytics, into SMO holds immense promise for enhancing network and energy efficiency, improving service quality and user satisfaction, enabling end-to-end (E2E) automation and full programmability, and facilitating proactive decision-making in dynamic and complex network environments [5], [6]. By leveraging ML algorithms, O-RAN can unlock valuable insights from vast volumes of data, predict and mitigate potential issues, automate repetitive tasks to

streamline operations, and make well-informed decisions [7], [8]. The overarching objective of leveraging ML is to empower predominantly autonomous and intelligent O-RAN capable of self-configuration, self-monitoring, self-healing, and self-optimization with minimal human intervention [6], [8].

The considerable potential impact of AI/ML in O-RAN has garnered significant research interest, as evidenced by various research papers. Some studies, such as [5] and [9], propose general frameworks for the intelligentization and automation of O-RAN, addressing various use cases enhanced by data analytics and intelligence. Other studies focus on specific aspects within O-RAN, optimizing certain performance metrics. For example, research has delved into exploring scheduling policy for various types of O-RAN slices [8], designing xApps for deep reinforcement learning-based closed-loop control of O-RAN slicing [10], dynamic offloading of O-RAN disaggregation to edge sites for local data processing and faster decision-making [11], proposing a programmable traffic control service model for O-RAN [12], and addressing the placement and scaling of O-RAN virtual NF [13]. Beyond applying AI/ML to the operations of O-RAN, there have been efforts to explore specific ML models for deploying and testing optimal intelligence and automation solutions within O-RAN. Examples of such studies include those referenced in [14] and [15]. In [14], the authors propose an automated, distributed, and AI-enabled testing framework designed to evaluate the decision-making performance, vulnerability, and security of AI models deployed within O-RAN. Finally, in [15], the authors introduce a framework that determines the data necessary for training an ML model for O-RAN, demonstrating significant performance improvement compared to traditional methods.

The analysis of the state-of-the-art reveals a predominant focus on devising general frameworks and assessing specific optimization solutions for integrating ML into O-RAN. However, we have recently studied the integration of management data analytics (MDA) into the management frameworks of 3GPP and ETSI, as well as enhanced the Non-RT RIC AI/ML capabilities, within the context of SMO [16]. This study was conducted based on a unified and standard-compliant SMO framework proposed in [4]. To our knowledge, this was the first comprehensive study solely dedicated to the intelligentization and automation of SMO. Apart from our earlier work [16], it is crucial to note the limited focus thus far on harnessing ML algorithms and intelligence to enhance the capabilities of SMO within O-RAN.

With the aim of delving deeper into the intelligentization and automation of SMO, we build upon our previous work

[16] and make the following contributions in this article:

- We **introduce three deployment scenarios for integrating ML models into SMO**. The primary objective of these scenarios is to allow SMO to select an AI/ML integration solution (tailored to its deployment and behavior) from a range of AI/ML integration options.
- We **concentrate on one of the proposed scenarios, wherein the ML model undergoes training through a centralized ML paradigm**. In this contribution, our objective is to introduce a comprehensive architectural solution, illustrating the E2E workflow of an ML model within the proposed centralized framework.
- We **identify several research challenges linked to the integration of a centralized ML paradigm within the SMO framework**. Addressing these challenges necessitates significant research endeavors to fulfill the escalating demands for enhancing the intelligence of SMO and facilitating the automation and intelligentization of various use cases related to the M&O of O-RAN components.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows: We commence by introducing three scenarios for the training and deployment of ML models within SMO in Section II. Then, we shift our attention to one of the scenarios, centralized ML, highlighting the proposed architectural solution and procedures in Section III. Next, we identify major research challenges associated with the centralized ML solution in Section IV. Finally, we summarize key points and identify promising directions for future research in Section V.

II. DEPLOYMENT SCENARIOS FOR INTEGRATING MDA INTO THE SMO FRAMEWORK

To integrate MDA¹ into SMO, aiming to enhance its M&O capabilities, we propose the consideration of a minimum of three scenarios for AI/ML model training, hosting, deployment, and monitoring, as shown in Figure 1. The three scenarios are outlined as follows: Scenario A: External Data or Model Importation; Scenario B: Internal Model Training and Deployment; and Scenario C: Collaborative Data or Model Sharing. These scenarios have been formulated upon the foundation of a unified SMO we proposed in [4], complemented by our research on the intelligentization and automation of SMO in [16]. In general, the three scenarios we present highlight various approaches to training, hosting, monitoring, and integrating AI/ML models into the operations of SMO.

Each scenario offers its own set of advantages and challenges. Selecting the most suitable scenario hinges on various factors, including the specific use case, the expertise of network operators, the availability and confidentiality of data, as well as the volume of raw data to be exchanged between

¹In this paper, the terms “MDA,” “intelligence,” and “AI/ML models” are used interchangeably to denote the application of advanced computational techniques for extracting insights, making well-informed decisions, and optimizing management processes within O-RAN in an intelligent and autonomous manner. Throughout the article, these terms convey the same meaning and are employed synonymously to emphasize the utilization of data-driven approaches for enhancing managerial intelligence within SMO.

data-producing sources and model training components. Furthermore, determining an optimal AI/ML model training and deployment scenario for the automation and intelligentization of SMO also depends on the metrics used to evaluate the performance of the respective AI/ML algorithm.

The metrics used to evaluate the performance of an AI/ML model may include training time, inference time, cost and resource requirements, time-to-detection, time-to-resolution, and other relevant factors. Nevertheless, our unified and interoperable SMO framework, presented in [4], aims to provide a flexible and extensible architectural solution that supports the three previously mentioned deployment scenarios as well as other potential configurations that may be explored in the future. This capability enables seamless integration and interoperability with other standards-based AI/ML model providers, data-producing sources, and data-consuming components. In the remaining part of this section, we delve into each deployment scenario, providing a detailed discussion of its architecture, components, interfaces, and processes.

A. Scenario A: External Data or Model Importation

In this scenario, the Non-RT RIC imports cleansed data or a trained AI/ML model from an External AI/ML Service Providing Source via an External AI/ML Interface. The External AI/ML Services are provided by external components (i.e., beyond the scope of O-RAN) and can be anchored outside of SMO [4]. For example, the Non-RT RIC framework imports a trained model or cleansed data from the ETSI Experiential Networked Intelligence (ENI) framework [17] or AI as a service (AIaaS) providing platform, which can be situated outside of SMO. The External AI/ML Service Provider must offer the necessary infrastructure and tools for data preprocessing, model training, and validation, aligning with best practices in machine learning operations (MLOps). It collects data from components within SMO. Data collection can be achieved via standard-compliant Application Programming Interfaces (APIs) to secure authorized access to the SMO components and retrieve the necessary management data.

By identifying the relevant data sources and understanding the API documentation, the External AI/ML Service Provider can make API requests to gather the required management data and subsequently store it within an appropriate storage system. Following these steps, as depicted in Figure 1, the External AI/ML Service Provider can effectively preprocess and prepare management data for training. This involves crucial data operations (DataOps) practices such as data cleansing, normalization, and the creation of training and validation datasets. Upon completion of data preparation, the External AI/ML Service Provider proceeds with the selection and training of the AI/ML model, aligning it with the specific requirements of the use case. The model training process is conducted offline, utilizing the cleansed management data in a manner widely recognized as a best practice. The trained model and cleansed data must undergo rigorous testing and validation procedures before being deployed to the Non-RT RIC. Upon completion of these processes, the cleansed data and the trained model

Fig. 1. Three scenarios for incorporating AI/ML models into SMO are depicted. The scopes of Scenario A, Scenario B, and Scenario C are portrayed within the dashed blue, red, and green boxes, respectively. The legends contained within this figure have been defined in our previous work [4].

are prepared for seamless deployment to the Non-RT RIC.

The importation of either the externally cleansed data or the trained AI/ML model to the Non-RT RIC is accomplished by utilizing the External AI/ML Termination via the External AI/ML Interface [4], as illustrated in Figure 1. The External AI/ML Termination is a logical function that can be anchored within the architecture of the Non-RT RIC. Upon successful importation of either the trained model or cleansed data, the AI/ML Function, which is a logical function and can also be anchored within the Non-RT RIC framework [16], takes over sole responsibility for their E2E lifecycle management. The decision of whether to import cleansed data or a trained model is a deployment choice made by the network operator.

In the event of importing cleansed data, the AI/ML Function assumes the responsibility for selecting, training, testing, and validating the appropriate AI/ML model before its execution. If the Non-RT RIC imports the model, the AI/ML Function must validate the model to ensure it meets the requirements of the use case and adheres to all privacy, security, and regulatory standards. Once the model, whether imported or trained within the Non-RT RIC, is prepared for execution, the AI/ML Function integrates it into the appropriate component(s) within SMO, aiming to enhance the performance of an optimization function. In this scenario, the Non-RT RIC may assume the responsibility for training (either online or offline), model selection, and lifecycle management, taking

into consideration the imported management data. On the other hand, the Non-RT RIC's role in handling the imported AI/ML model may be limited to hosting, deployment, monitoring, and continuous improvement.

B. Scenario B: Internal Model Training and Deployment

The Non-RT RIC collects raw management data from various data-producing management systems and components within SMO via standard-compliant interfaces. The Non-RT RIC then cleanses and normalizes the collected data, as well as trains, tests, validates, executes, and monitors the selected AI/ML model. This specifically means that the AI/ML Function within the Non-RT RIC collects and utilizes management data originating from the intelligent systems of the 3GPP-network slicing management system (3GPP-NSMS), NFV-management and orchestration (NFV-MANO), and other M&O systems and components, as depicted in Figure 1. In this article, we adopt the MDA System as the intelligent system of the 3GPP-NSMS and NFV-MANO. Specific details regarding this adoption and the AI/ML Function are elaborated in [16].

The 3GPP-NSMS can encompass entities such as the network slice subnet management function (NSSMF) and the network function management functions (NFMFs) [18]. The NFV-MANO may incorporate several functional blocks (FBs) and MFs [18], including the network function virtualization orchestrator (NFVO), virtual network function manager (VNFM), virtualized infrastructure manager (VIM), wide area

network infrastructure manager (WIM), container infrastructure service management (CISM), container image registry (CIR), and container infrastructure service cluster management (CCM). The Non-RT RIC may also collect data from other *de facto* and *de jure* management systems and components that operate within SMO and generate M&O services for O-RAN. The components of each intelligent system are interconnected with the components of its respective management system via standardized and interoperable interfaces [16].

The AI/ML Function of the Non-RT RIC can collect the corresponding management data from the intelligent systems of the 3GPP-NSMS and NFV-MANO through the use of NSSMF Termination and NFVO Termination via the NSSMF_NonRTRIC and NFVO_NonRTRIC interfaces, respectively. We initially introduced these two terminations and their relevant interfaces in our previous work [4]. We further expanded upon these terminations and their respective interfaces in another paper of ours referenced in [16], enhancing their capabilities to facilitate the exchange of training data and AI/ML models between the 3GPP-NSMS, NFV-MANO, and Non-RT RIC within SMO. Once the data has been collected by the two terminations, the NSSMF Termination and the NFVO Termination seamlessly facilitate the transfer of collected data to the AI/ML Function via the SMO internal interfaces.

Immediately upon receiving the relevant management data, the AI/ML Function commences the process of cleansing, normalizing, and preparing the data for validation, training, and testing. Subsequently, the AI/ML Function undertakes the training (offline or online) of the selected AI/ML model, hosts it, executes it within SMO, continuously monitors its performance, and manages it throughout its operational lifespan. If the chosen model has successfully completed training and testing, the AI/ML Function expeditiously transfers the executable AI/ML model to the NSSMF Termination and NFVO Termination via designated SMO internal interfaces.

The two terminations then take on the responsibility of conveying recommendations or predictions generated by the recently-trained AI/ML model through their respective interfaces to the management systems and components, namely the 3GPP-NSMS and NFV-MANO. These management systems utilize the outputs of the trained model to improve the performance of a certain optimization function within SMO. They also provide periodic reports to the AI/ML Function by supplying up-to-date management data. This process contributes to the improvement of the deployed AI/ML model through continuous online training. In this scenario, the Non-RT RIC holds exclusive responsibility for the intelligentization and automation of the operations and maintenance of SMO.

C. Scenario C: Collaborative Data or Model Sharing

In this scenario, the management data-producing components and systems within SMO deliver either cleansed data or trained AI/ML models to the Non-RT RIC via SMO internal interfaces. The Non-RT RIC then assumes the crucial responsibility of constructing a global model that enhances the performance of an optimization function within O-RAN.

It specifically means that the AI/ML Function either collects cleansed data or trained local AI/ML models from the MDA System of the 3GPP-NSMS and the MDA System of the NFV-MANO, as shown in Figure 1. The AI/ML Function aggregates these individual local models or trains the cleansed data with the goal of constructing a global model.

The local models, also referred to as domain-level models in this article, are trained within specific management domains (i.e., NFV-MANO, 3GPP-NSMS, and other systems within SMO), utilizing the management data or network data stored on such domains. These models guarantee that confidential information remains stored on the respective management domains and is only transmitted when absolutely required or at specified time intervals, hence protecting user privacy and data security. The global model is trained using the cleansed data or trained local models stored within the central repository of data and models of the AI/ML Function. This model incorporates the collective learnings from cleansed data or all the local models of the MDA Systems of the 3GPP-NSMS and NFV-MANO. It acts as the coordinator, periodically aggregating updates from local models and incorporating them into its own parameters.

The MDA System of the 3GPP-NSMS collects management data and network data from the NSSMF, NFMFs, and the NFs of an open next generation node B (O-gNB). It undertakes data cleansing, conducts training for MF-level/NF-level and domain-level models, and subsequently executes these models to automate the operations of the corresponding MFs and the entire 3GPP-NSMS. MF-level and NF-level models are tailored models that are trained and executed specifically for a given MF or NF, respectively. The trained models and cleansed data of the 3GPP-NSMS can be stored within its respective MDA System for archival purposes. Depending on the configuration, the MDA System may transfer either the cleansed data or the trained models to the NSSMF Termination via the NSSMF_NonRTRIC interface. The NSSMF Termination may subsequently transfer the cleansed data or the trained models to the AI/ML Function via the SMO internal interface.

The MDA System of the NFV-MANO collects management data and network data from the MFs, FBs, and the underlying infrastructure. The MDA System performs data cleansing, normalization, and data preparation tasks. Additionally, it engages in the training, validation, and testing processes for the corresponding models. Once the MF-level, NF-level, and domain-level models have been trained, the MDA System executes them to intelligentize the operations of the FBs, MFs, NF, and the entire NFV-MANO. Based on the chosen design, the MDA System of the NFV-MANO may transfer either the cleansed data or the trained domain-level models to the NFVO Termination via the NFVO_NonRTRIC interface. The NFVO Termination then forwards them via Non-RT RIC internal interfaces to the AI/ML Function for additional processing.

If the Non-RT RIC is configured to import cleansed data from the 3GPP-NSMS and NFV-MANO, the AI/ML Function is then responsible for the validation, training, and testing of the global AI/ML model. Following the testing phase, it is an-

anticipated that the AI/ML Function will develop an accurate and reliable global model. In the instance where the Non-RT RIC imports trained domain-level models, the AI/ML Function constructs the global model by aggregating the 3GPP-NSMS and NFV-MANO models. Once the global model (whether derived from imported cleansed data or domain-level trained models) is constructed and ready for deployment, the AI/ML Function provides it to the NFVO Termination and NSSMF Termination via the SMO internal interfaces.

The two terminations provide the global model to the MDA Systems of the NFV-MANO and 3GPP-NSMS via the `NFVO_NonRTRIC` and `NSSMF_NonRTRIC` interfaces, respectively. The two MDA Systems utilize the global model to enhance the performance and generalizability of their respective domain-level models. By providing access to a larger dataset, enforcing consistency, handling heterogeneity, correcting errors, and forming an ensemble, the global model can help domain-level models learn more accurately and generalize better to unseen data. This collaborative approach between domain-level and global models is a key enabler of federated learning, allowing us to develop AI/ML models that are both privacy-preserving and highly effective.

In Scenario C, the Non-RT RIC holds a partial role in the intelligentization and automation of the operations associated with SMO. The scope of the Non-RT RIC might be restricted to that of Scenario A. Hence, continuous interactions among the components and interfaces of SMO are essential to facilitate enhanced AI/ML model delivery and refinement.

III. CENTRALIZED ML MODEL TRAINING AND DEPLOYMENT SOLUTIONS WITHIN SMO

Following the introduction of three scenarios for integrating ML models into SMO, we now focus on Scenario B. In this scenario, data is gathered at a single centralized location – the Non-RT RIC. The selected model is trained using this data, deployed across SMO, and continuously refined. In this section, we outline a detailed workflow for realizing centralized ML model training within the Non-RT RIC and its deployment across SMO. The proposed workflow consists of three phases, as shown in Figure 2: (a) data collection and preprocessing; (b) model training and development; and (c) model deployment and inference. By conscientiously following the three phases, robust and effective ML models can be developed that deliver valuable results for the intended optimization problem. In the following, we discuss these three phases, respectively.

A. Data Collection and Preprocessing

This phase involves gathering and organizing the requisite data for training a selected ML model within the Non-RT RIC. The data is collected at the AI/ML Function from diverse sources located within the 3GPP-NSMS, NFV-MANO, Non-RT RIC itself, and potentially other systems reside within SMO via standard-compliant interfaces. The Non-RT RIC can employ techniques such as streaming and batch collection to capture both real-time and historical data from the aforementioned sources. The collected data primarily encompasses

real-time operational data pertaining to network management, service orchestration, and SMO performance.

Within the 3GPP-NSMS, the NFMFs hold a rich set of management data related to the M&O of open centralized unit (O-CU), open distributed unit (O-DU), and open radio unit (O-RU). These NFMFs collect and provide such data to the NSSMF. The NSSMF holds its own data and that of its associated NFMFs. We assume that the NSSMF, alongside its fundamental functionalities, possesses the capability to generate and utilize AI/ML services within the 3GPP-NSMS. Based on this assumption, the NSSMF, on behalf of the MDA System of the 3GPP-NSMS, provides raw management data via the `NSSMF_NonRTRIC` interface to NSSMF Termination. Subsequently, this data is transferred to the AI/ML Function via SMO internal interfaces for further processing.

The FBs and MFs within the NFV-MANO, as discussed in the preceding section, contain management data associated with the virtual and cloud-native aspects of an O-gNB and the underlying wireless infrastructure. Each MF and FB collects and holds its respective data. This data can then be transmitted to and stored within the NFVO. Assuming that the NFVO, in addition to its core functionalities, possesses the capability to produce and consume AI/ML services. Hence, under the authority of the MDA System of the NFV-MANO, the NFVO furnishes management data pertaining to the NFV-MANO via the `NFVO_NonRTRIC` interface to the NFVO Termination. Furthermore, this data is conveyed to the AI/ML Function via SMO internal interfaces for subsequent treatment.

The AI/ML Function gathers relevant data from the components of the Non-RT RIC framework and the rApps via the R1 interface and the internal interfaces of the Non-RT RIC. In addition, the AI/ML Function can collect corresponding data from other de facto and de jure management systems within SMO via internal interfaces specific to the SMO.

Once the data has been completely gathered from the aforementioned data sources and stored within the AI/ML Function, it may contain errors, inconsistencies, and irrelevant information, necessitating preprocessing and polishing. Data preprocessing addresses these critical issues by cleansing, formatting, and transforming the collected data into a usable format for the ML model, as shown in Figure 2. During the cleansing process, the AI/ML Function removes duplicated data, corrects errors, and handles missing values. In the formatting process, it standardizes collected data into a common format, facilitating comparisons. In the transformation process, the AI/ML Function scales features, converts categorical data to numerical data (i.e., encoding), and performs feature engineering (i.e., creating new features from existing ones).

Following the above procedures, the AI/ML Function undertakes exploratory data analysis on preprocessed data, as shown in Figure 2. During this process, various techniques such as visualization and statistical analysis are utilized to delve into the dataset, aiming to understand crucial variables, their correlations, magnitudes, and statistical attributes concerning the target variable. This process serves to pinpoint potential issues, guide decisions throughout model development, and distin-

Fig. 2. Proposed workflow for centralized ML model training, deployment, and refinement within the SMO framework of O-RAN architecture

guish between valuable features and irrelevant ones within the dataset. By executing these procedures, the data is assumed to be prepared for subsequent processes and consequently delivered to the second phase within the proposed workflow, as discussed in the following and illustrated in Figure 2.

B. Model Training and Development

Once the collected data has undergone preprocessing and validation, and has been successfully received by this phase, the AI/ML Function proceeds to initiate the training and development of a selected ML model. The Model Training and Development phase encompasses crucial processes in ML model lifecycle management, including appropriate model selection, training, and development, as illustrated in Figure 2. Each process within this phase holds significant importance in crafting resilient and efficient ML models tailored to address specific optimization problems within O-RAN.

During the model selection process, the initial crucial step is to clearly define the optimization problem that the model aims to address, as depicted in Figure 2. A comprehensive understanding of the optimization problem thoroughly guides the selection of appropriate ML algorithms. Depending on the problem type, data characteristics, and computational resources available, a set of candidate ML models is chosen. Common choices encompass linear regression, support vector

machines, decision trees, and neural networks, among many others. Due to privacy and security concerns, the AI/ML Function is also responsible for determining whether an AI/ML model shall be deployed in a federated or centralized manner before starting to collect data from data sources.

Selecting an optimal centralized ML model requires a robust evaluation strategy. This entails dividing the data into training, validation, and test sets, as shown in Figure 2. The model is then trained on the training set and assessed on the validation set to fine-tune hyperparameters, which are the configurations of the model. Finally, the performance of the model is evaluated on the unseen test set. To that end, a common set of evaluation metrics includes accuracy for classification tasks or mean squared error for regression tasks.

During the process of training an ML model, the selected model is subjected to training using a training dataset. Throughout this training step, the model undergoes a learning process wherein it discerns and internalizes the complex patterns and relationships inherent within the data. Hyperparameter tuning emerges as a critical step in enhancing the performance of the selected model.

Within the context of ML, hyperparameters are configurations that govern the learning process of an ML model, such as the learning rate or the depth of a decision tree. Adjusting these hyperparameters can significantly impact the effectiveness and efficiency of the model. Techniques like grid search and randomized search are commonly employed to explore various combinations of hyperparameters, identifying the optimal settings that result in superior performance on the validation set during the training process.

In the model development process, the performance of the trained ML model is carefully evaluated on the hold-out test set. This step provides an unbiased estimate of how well the model will generalize to unseen data. Based on the evaluation metrics, the best-performing ML model from the candidate pool is selected. Furthermore, understanding how the model arrives at its predictions can be crucial. Techniques such as feature importance analysis help identify which features have the most significant influence on the model's output. This insight can provide a valuable understanding of the target optimization problem domain within O-RAN, aiding in informed decision-making and AI/ML model refinement.

C. Model Deployment and Inference

If the trained ML model performs optimally, it can be deployed into a production environment for real-time or near-real-time inference. The production environments include the 3GPP-NSMS, NFV-MANO, and other systems within the SMO. The AI/ML Function performs the model deployment and inference via the NSSMF_NonRTRIC, NFVO_NonRTRIC, R1, and other standard-compliant interfaces. This phase entails integrating the ML model into the aforementioned management systems, where it can be utilized for real-time predictions or task automation. Additionally, this phase may involve a refinement process wherein the performance of the deployed model is continuously monitored and

periodically retrained with new data to ensure its continued effectiveness in addressing optimization tasks within O-RAN.

In this phase, several critical steps must be followed, as illustrated in Figure 2. First, the selection of a deployment environment is paramount. This entails deciding whether the trained model will reside on on-premises servers, cloud platforms, or edge devices. The location where the model is executed depends on the requirements of the optimization problem. For specific services like ultra-reliable and low-latency communications (URLLC), it may be necessary for the model to be executed at the edge, such as at the NFMF, to effectively optimize the management of these services. Following determining the deployment environment, containerization becomes a crucial consideration, though optional. Packaging the ML model, along with its dependencies, into a container like Docker ensures consistency across diverse environments, facilitating seamless deployment transitions. Scalability considerations form another pivotal aspect of deployment planning. Analyzing factors like anticipated workload, concurrent requests, and resource utilization aids in devising a deployment strategy that accommodates varying levels of demand [18].

Furthermore, robust monitoring and refining mechanisms are essential for optimizing the performance of the deployed model. Implementing a monitoring system within the AI/ML Function to track input data, predictions, and encountered errors provides valuable insights for continual improvement and refinement of the deployed model. Before refining the model, it is essential to assess its current performance using relevant evaluation metrics. These metrics could vary depending on the specific optimization problem as well as the characteristics and objectives of the model. Conducting a thorough analysis to identify areas where the model may be underperforming or exhibiting undesirable behavior is of vital importance. This analysis may involve examining misclassified samples, exploring feature importance, or analyzing model biases.

Once the AI/ML Function receives feedback, the model can embark on a second attempt to enhance the outcome, as depicted in Figure 2. In this phase, the algorithm incorporates feedback from the initial iteration and initiates improvements accordingly. As the model undergoes refinement, it yields a more polished output, thereby aiding in training the system to better comprehend real-world scenarios and expectations. Finally, by carefully navigating through these steps, a well-deployed model can fulfill its intended purpose effectively and securely, instilling confidence in its reliability and integrity.

IV. MAJOR RESEARCH CHALLENGES

This section outlines several research challenges linked to implementing AI/ML solutions centrally within SMO. Addressing these challenges demands considerable research efforts to align with the escalating demands of future-oriented SMO frameworks. It also aims to facilitate the M&O of the emerging use cases and applications within O-RAN.

A. Privacy

The first technical challenge arising from the SMO-centralized AI/ML solution is data privacy. In Scenario B, the

raw management data collected from various sources within SMO may contain sensitive information, such as non-access stratum signaling data. Consistently transmitting such data to the Non-RT RIC and maintaining it therewith for model training and development poses an increased risk of data exposure and privacy breaches, particularly in scenarios where midhaul connections are established wirelessly. To address this challenge effectively, the AI/ML Function must implement robust data privacy mechanisms to ensure that sensitive information is protected. These mechanisms may include data anonymization, encryption, and secure data transmission protocols. Furthermore, the AI/ML Function must adhere to data protection regulations, such as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) in the European Union, to safeguard user privacy throughout the data processing lifecycle.

B. Resilience

Ensuring the resilience of the centralized framework, particularly against data poisoning attacks, emerges as another critical concern. Centralized learning methodologies are inherently vulnerable to compromised raw data [19]. In the context of SMO, the raw data to train the AI/ML model may be tampered with, potentially leading to inaccurate predictions and suboptimal performance. Possible approaches to realizing such tampering include hijacking or manipulating user equipment to generate abnormal network behavior, or directly injecting malicious data packets into the raw management data pipeline or database. To effectively address this challenge, the AI/ML Function must implement robust data validation mechanisms to detect and filter out compromised data.

C. Elasticity

Commonly in practice, the centralized AI/ML models must be occasionally retrained to keep up with the evolving network conditions and user requirements. However, such retraining often requires significant computational resources. By sharing the resources of a Non-RT RIC with other NFs, the retraining procedures may trigger resource contention and degrade network performance. To achieve optimal elasticity, it calls for well-designed virtual resource scheduling at the Non-RT RIC that can adapt to changing workload patterns and adaptively prioritize the needs of the AI/ML Function and other NFs.

D. Agility

In addition to elasticity, the agility of the centralized AI/ML model emerges as another critical challenge, particularly concerning model retraining. While the model is trained using a vast amount of data aggregated from different domains, which usually takes a long time to converge, the network conditions, traffic patterns, and user requirements may change rapidly in individual local areas. It becomes therefore a crucial issue, how the centralized model in AI/ML Function can quickly adapt to the dynamic local environments, ensuring its continued effectiveness and accuracy in real-time scenarios. To tackle this challenge, advanced approaches are essential to enable the model to continuously and agilely learn and adapt to local variations and dynamics. This may involve incremental learning techniques, such as Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGD)

[20], which allow to efficiently update a trained model based on only the differential data, instead of retraining the model from scratch on with the entire dataset. Nevertheless, this may also introduce new challenges related to incremental learning techniques, e.g., model drift and catastrophic forgetting.

E. Signaling Efficiency

Even with optimal learning efficiency that resolves the challenges of elasticity and agility, the inherent design of the centralized AI/ML solution, which involves aggregating massive amounts of raw data, gives rise to a significant signaling overhead. This overhead can potentially lead to network congestion at the midhaul, consequently causing heightened latency and diminished quality of service (QoS).

F. Robustness and Reliability

Finally, the centralized framework is vulnerable to single-point failures. If the centralized model or the AI/ML Function fails, the entire M&O procedures will be disrupted, leading to a significant degradation in network performance, or even malfunctions. To mitigate this challenge, the AI/ML Function must implement robust fault tolerance mechanisms to ensure the reliability of the centralized models and AI/ML Function. This may involve replicating the AI/ML Function across multiple Non-RT RIC instances to ensure high availability and fault tolerance. Notably, this necessitates the establishment of external data/model importation mechanisms, as discussed in Scenario A, to enable warm/hot backups. By implementing these measures, the centralized framework can withstand single-point failures and maintain operational continuity, thereby safeguarding network performance and stability.

V. CONCLUDING REMARKS AND FUTURE OUTLOOK

This article has presented three scenarios for integrating AI/ML algorithms into the SMO framework. Through these scenarios, we have outlined how SMO can evolve to address the burgeoning demands of managing the complex O-RAN interfaces and components. Our focus then narrowed to a detailed exploration of one scenario, centralized ML, where we have proposed an architectural solution. The proposal positioned the Non-RT RIC as a central entity responsible for data collection as well as training, deploying, and refining the ML model. However, the proposed solution presents a number of challenges that demand innovative solutions. Hence, we have identified several research challenges that require exploration to further enhance the intelligence of SMO.

Regarding future work, we aim to delve into the exploration of Scenario A and Scenario C, as proposed in this article. In Scenario A, our focus lies on studying the mechanisms for data collection and model training from an external source. Once the model is prepared for deployment, the AI/ML Function may import it to incorporate the model into an optimization task. In Scenario B, our interest lies in exploring distributed learning techniques, particularly federated learning, tailored specifically for SMO. The goal of this investigation could involve training and developing a global model for SMO, wherein one management system, such as Non-RT RIC, could

act as a model aggregator, while other systems, such as 3GPP-NSMS and NFV-MANO, serve as clients. By addressing these research challenges, future studies can contribute to the ongoing evolution of SMO, driving innovation and efficiency in network and service M&O within O-RAN.

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